

Opinions of Indian and Global Leaders on the Means of Liberating Portuguese Territories in India on the Historical Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

India gained independence after a prolonged struggle against British on 15 August 1947. However, the presence of Portuguese and French in post-Indian independence disappointed many nationalists and further, they felt the liberation against the foreign rule in India was incomplete and that led to the series of movements in India and Portuguese territories. The developing events forced the Indian government under the leadership of our first Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru to rethink the possible way to liberate and finally he could achieve the task on 19 December 1961 and incorporated the territories into the Indian Union in 1962. Mr. Narayan said it was a great pity that India had to resort to force in Goa. But politically no alternative was open to it. "The Hindu, Madras edition said on December 20, 1961, after the campaign was over", it would be presenting a deceptive picture to suggest that everyone is supremely happy over the Goa developments without any reservation. Many in high places did hold a different view on the desirability of using force. The fear is that by her action India might have endangered the high esteem in which she has been held all over the world. These leaders, however, realize that the criticism India must face is not so much about the taking over of Portuguese colonies but of doing it in a way which went against her professions and principles". Thus the above opinions make it very clear even though Indians were successful in ousting Portuguese from India, Indian leaders though were very happy to see the liberated people of Portuguese territories in India, were slightly unhappy over the approach to achieve it.

Key Words: Independence, Prolonged struggle, Portuguese colonies, Leaders, liberation.

Introduction

The story of the liberation of Portuguese territories in India was not only one of the most important events of contemporary India but even of the World. India gained independence after a prolonged struggle against British on 15 August 1947. However, the presence of Portuguese and French in post-Indian independence disappointed many nationalists and further, they felt the liberation against the foreign rule in India was incomplete and that led to the series of movements in India and Portuguese territories. The developing events forced the Indian government under the leadership of our first Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru to rethink the possible way to liberate and finally he could achieve the task on 19 December 1961 and incorporated the territories into the Indian Union in 1962. But the annexation was recognized by Portugal only in 1975.

Liberating Portuguese Territories in India on the Historical Perspectives

The objective of the paper is to understand the views or opinions of national and global leaders on the means of achieving the objective or liberating so called Portuguese territories in India. With the end of Portuguese rule, a chapter in the history of colonialism comes to an end and a new era dawn for the people. It is now possible to present a complete picture of Goa in its proper perspective in a chronological narrative. The jubilation of Indians on that December day was like that on Independence Day in 1947. In the words of Prime Minister Nehru, "nothing has happened in India, since Independence, fourteen and a half years ago, which has excited and thrilled the people of India as this liberation of Goa". Thus, India woke up on December 18, 1961, to learn with joy that Indian troops had entered Goa, Daman, and Diu to liberate them. Newspapers announced the news with banner headings; people listened to radios in houses, cafes, and shops to hear the latest on Goa. The police action did not come as a complete surprise to the nation.¹

Thanks to the Indian Government and our former Prime Minister for untiring efforts to liberate Portuguese territories in India. This initiative was appreciated as well as condemned by many. Firstly, the friendly countries of Portugal and their allies of NATO condemned India for using violence to force Portugal to surrender. In this regard, Nehru said "on the Goa issue certain people had held that India's policy of non-alignment and peace and befriending others had undergone a radical change. "I want to make it quite clear", he said, "that our policy has not changed in the slightest because of Goa. I don't understand how anyone can say that we acted in Goa by changing

our policy or going against it.” Further, he said he would have been happy if the Goa issue had been settled peacefully. But India was compelled by Portuguese intransigence to act. There was no other way. “It is correct that I was not very happy over sending our forces to Goa, but it was done because of compelling circumstances”, he said. “You know that in this world, on various political and other matters we have to say and do things which we do not out of happiness, but because of compelling forces.” He did not know how Gandhiji would have felt over it, and what advice he would have given. But Gandhiji was up for seeing men and had blessed the moving in of the Indian armed forces to defend Kashmir.²

He further staunchly denies that his use of force to wrest the enclaves of Goa, Daman, and Diu² from Portuguese rule was inconsistent with his preaching of peaceful methods. He notes that New Delhi had tried repeatedly in vain to negotiate with Lisbon for the transfer of Portuguese possessions on the India subcontinent.³ “Holding to non-violence,” Nehru commented, “his non-violence was more of the mind and thought also of action, but more than that. He said, if you have a dagger in your heart, pull it out and use it and not keep it in your mind and heart.” Many Westerners feel that Nehru’s post-Goa comments merely reflected a searching for an excuse to justify an action that, had it been committed by another country, India would have condemned. They feel that if he thinks he can justify the use of force to settle some international disputes, he should have expressed such a view long ago in other issues, rather than attempt to pass moral judgment in a supposed quest to avoid violence. The biggest factor that induced India to use force against the Portuguese was probably an overwhelming frustration that resulted from failure to oust them peacefully. To most Indians, the Portuguese enclaves represented the last vestiges of an archaic colonialism that had lived far beyond its time. Some commentators feel that the United States, which was emotionally upset by the military takeover, should have used its influence long before to try to persuade Lisbon to consider a peaceful change. Another factor that probably helped to induce India was a threatened weakening of its prestige in Asian and African affairs. India’s peaceful approach, although it had lent more than 5,800 troops and planes and equipment to the UN force in the Congo and his troops with the UN in Gaza placed it out of step with the military anti-colonial clamor in parts of Africa. To many African freedom fighters, who have seen repression that was rarely known in India, the New Delhi approach was difficult to accept.⁴

The policy that we have pursued has been, even as in India under British rule, one of non-violence, and we have fashioned our approach and conduct accordingly. This adherence to non-violence means that we may not abandon or permit any derogation of our identification with the cause of our compatriots under Portuguese rule and equally, we may not adopt, advocate or deliberately bring about the situations of violence.

We regard and base our position on the fact that the liberation movement in Goa was spontaneous, and that its real strength lies in this fact. The Government of India and I am confident, the great majority of our people, have no intention of adopting any policy or methods which depart from these principles, which are the foundations on which our very nationhood rests and which are the historic and unique legacy of Gandhi and the pioneers of our freedom.⁵

The chief United States delegate, Mr. Adlai Stevenson's speech in the Security Council on December 19th came as a rude shock to India because it never expected him to use such strong language. It was difficult to understand his arguments. If the invasion of Egypt, Cuba, and Hungary by powerful permanent council members did not weaken the world organization, how could India's action to liberate a part of its territory produce such a disaster? The Soviet Union vetoed the resolution and saved India the embarrassment of having to ignore a resolution of the council.

Mr. Stevenson's harsh words against India did not impair Indo-U.S. relations. This is largely because of the vast understanding between the two Governments and their people. The U.S. knew the reluctance with which India took the final decision, India postponed the action twice after fixing "vague dates" first when some Latin American countries wanted to bring about a peaceful settlement and on the second occasion on a suggestion from the U.S. itself. Only after the United States informed India that the "Portuguese response to the American initiative had been a negative one", did this country decide in favor of police action and that too most reluctantly. The action came after India and other friendly nations had given up the hope of a peaceful settlement. All the same, the anxiety of the U.S. Government to help in solving this issue was much appreciated by India. Thanks to the efforts of President John F. Kennedy and the American Ambassador in India, Mr. J.K. Galbraith, Indo- U.S. relations are at their most felicitous at present.⁶ On the other hand, Mr. Nehru said that it was unimaginable, how any intelligent man in the world, especially in the western countries could expect India to tolerate the continuance of Portuguese colonialism on Indian soil. India had every right to overthrow given by force as it had the right to use force in throwing out

British imperialism. India adopting a different course which was a good course, but that did not take away India's right to use force to throw out a foreign imperialist sitting on its chest.⁷ He added further that “Taking any military action is contrary to my gain. It hurts me to do it. I could only agree to this because the consequences of not taking it would have been very harmful even from the point of view of violence.”⁸

Thus, ruling out violence, this is the only alternative left to her, consistent with honor. India has waited long enough. She should not wait any longer. Portugal, knowing India’s non-violence attitude, took advantage of it. She has nothing to worry. India must do something to show that she is quite serious about it, that she is vehemently in earnest and means business this time. Let the moral issue come to the force.⁹ In short, he made it very clear in his speech which he made at his public meeting at Chowpathy, Mr. Nehru mentioned why and made him adopt a measure which was objected by the countries of the world to liberate the Portuguese territories in India.¹⁰

Mr. Nehru said “Our Army, Navy and the Air force are strictly meant for defense purpose. We are more Army, Navy and Airforce with a view to defense. There used to be an expeditionary force in the British times. We have none. We are not going to send any force anywhere else. There is a weapon of war to strike at a long distance. We keep none of this. We have no intention of striking at a long distance. Our conception in keeping the Army, Navy and Air force is defense, effective defense, strong defense, but defense. Cold war, conflicts, hatred, etc., they will not vanish away quickly. All these things are there. Nevertheless, it does appear I do not think this is wishful thinking that humanity has taken a turn in the right direction. In that, many factors have worked. It would be completely wrong for anyone to say that this country or that country has brought it about. It is really because of the efforts of many countries and to a very small extent our efforts also that this thing is happening. In circumstances like these, more especially, we have the right to view every step that we take, even a small local step. In this context, I would have said even without this large context, following the general policy that we do, we should have considered this question of Goa and conclude that only peaceful methods should be employed. But, in this larger context, that becomes even more important.”¹¹

Thus India tried its best to stick to the non-violent policy but the violence and cruel methods used by the Portuguese Government on the nationalists and other freedom fighters and

that an acute frustration was developing among the brave Goans who had begun to feel that the Government of India was passive and not sincere in their protestations about freeing Goa.¹² Thus Portuguese and policies ultimately forced India to take armed action codenamed as “Operation Vijay” to defuse the Portuguese attack and surrender them within 24 hours.

People of Goa welcomed their liberation with immense enthusiasm and jubilation. It was an enthusiasm of a long gagged and silenced people giving vent to their pent-up and unexpressed emotions. It was an enthusiasm such as only deep and cherished dreams and hopes can kindle the hope of a new and better life.¹³ The liberation of Goa, Daman, and Diu brings that night of terror to an end and the people suffering for centuries emerge into the light and warmth of freedom at last. It is the end of an age in Asia and indirectly in Africa, for colonialism has been the curse of these two continents for more than 400 years. The Afro-Asian nations know it and express their jubilation in no uncertain terms. India’s prompt action is an example and a source of inspiration for other victims of Portuguese tyranny. A news agency message tells us that the African diplomats assembled at U.N headquarters expected similar action against Anglo and Mozambique unless the United Nations in the meanwhile found it possible to implement its own resolution against colonialism.¹⁴

Conclusion

Many appreciated the initiatives of the Indian Government. The Archbishop of Bombay, Cardinal of Roman Church and Bishop of Goa welcomed this victory and appreciated the people of Goa through telegrams. To this, the first act of President Rajendra Prasad, who resumed office on December 20’ 1961, after a prolonged illness congratulated the people of Goa and said it was their resistance to foreign domination and keenness to be free which broke up the colonial regime. He also praised the Indian armed forces for helping the people of Goa to end the colonial regime quickly, using only the minimum of force.

Mr. Jayaprakash Narayan, one of the noted followers of Mahatma Gandhi, fully justified the steps taken to integrate the Portuguese settlements. Mr. Narayan said it was a great pity that India had to resort to force in Goa. But politically no alternative was open to it. Though Indians of all shades of political opinion welcomed the integration of Goa into the Indian Union, many influential leaders were disturbed that force had been used, particularly in view of India’s consistent opposition

to the use of force and its known adherence to the principles of non-violence. “The Hindu, Madras edition said on December 20,1961, after the campaign was over”, it would be presenting a deceptive picture to suggest that everyone is supremely happy over the Goa developments without any reservation. Many in high places did hold a different view on the desirability of using force. If they remained publicly silent without ventilating their viewpoint, it is because they did not want to embarrass the government which had made up its mind and because they did not want to give the impression that they were opposed to Portugal’s exit from Indian soil. Their fear is that by her action India might have endangered the high esteem in which she has been held all over the world. These leaders, however, realize that the criticism India must face is not so much about the taking over of Portuguese colonies but of doing it in a way which went against her professions and principles”. Mr. Chakravarti Rajagopalachari, one of India’s most respected "elder statesmen," in an article on December 27 in Swarajya, the organ of the Swatantra Party said that India had “totally lost the moral power to raise her voice against militarism” and had helped to undermine the prestige and power of the Security Council whilst Portugal’s presence in Goa had been "an offense to Indian Nationalism.” It was not a greater offense than Communist China’s occupation of Indian Territory or the social evil created by untouchables; the treatment of a wide section of the Indian population as outcasts, which Gandhi had denounced as a “deadly sin”. For nearly half a century India had been sustained by the Gandhian principles of nonviolence, but the “great adventure” of seizing Goa might prove to be a turning point in India’s devotion to those principles. “The question is,” wrote Mr. Rajagopalachari, “what faith we now profess? What message does India now carry in a world on the brink of moral collapse? Our, nationalism has, I fear, led us into impatience at the wrong moment. We had a mission for promoting peace and a special qualification for fulfilling it”.¹⁵ Thus the above opinions make it very clear even though Indians were successful in ousting Portuguese from India, Indian leaders though were very happy to see the liberated people of Portuguese territories in India, were slightly unhappy over the approach to achieve it. It is so because India is well known for its policy of non-violence and forerunner of peace.

END NOTES

¹ Rao, R. P. Portuguese Rule in Goa 1510- 1961.p.1.

² Prime Minister on Goa. New Delhi.p.52-53.

³ Grimes, Paul. India: 15 Years of Freedom.p.49-50.

⁴ *Ibid.p50-51*

⁵ Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru’s Statement on Peaceful Liberation of Goa in Lok Sabha on August 25,1954)

⁶ Rao, R. P. Portuguese Rule in Goa 1510- 1961.p.6-7.

⁷ Prime Minister on Goa. New Delhi.p.44.

⁸ Rao, R. P. Portuguese Rule in Goa 1510- 1961.p.193\

⁹ Mahabharati, Alokandal. Abolition of Poverty - An Open Letter to Jawaharlal Nehru.p.24.

¹⁰ Handoo, G K. Goa wins Freedom - Reflections and Remniscences.p.194

¹¹ Debate in Lok Sabha on July 26, 1955,p.27.

¹² Handoo, G K. Goa wins Freedom - Reflections and Remniscences.p.

¹³ Braganca, Betha Menezes. Landmarks In My Time. Margao, Goa.p.45

¹⁴ Patrika, Amrita Bazar, ed. The Voice Of Patrika 1920 - 70.p.11.

¹⁵ Rao R. P. Portuguese Rule in Goa 1510- 1961.p.196.